

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF GREWIA ASIATICA L. TABLETS FOR THE TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

Abhishek Raj^{1*}, Dr. Amit Sharma²

¹PhD Scholar (Department of Pharmacy) Faculty of Medical, Paramedical and Allied Health Sciences, Jagannath University, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

²Dean (Medical, Paramedical and Allied Health Sciences) and HOD (Pharmacy), Jagannath University, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India.

***Corresponding Author: Abhishek Raj**

PhD Scholar (Department of Pharmacy) Faculty of Medical, Paramedical and Allied Health Sciences, Jagannath University, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17746601>

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this study was to formulate tablets containing fruits extract of *Grewia asiatica L.* in which the dose of Grewia extract was 500 mg. The tablets were prepared by wet granulation method using microcrystalline cellulose and mannitol as diluents; croscarmellose sodium, crospovidone and sodium starch glycolate as super disintegrants; Aerosil as a glidant and magnesium stearate as a lubricant. Any excipient in the form of a binder was not used as Grewia extract had a sticky nature and believed to act as a self-binder. Purified water was used as a solvent. The prepared tablets were evaluated for various physicochemical parameters such as drug-excipient interaction by FTIR, flow properties, hardness, weight variation, thickness, friability, disintegration time and uniformity of content. These tablets were also subjected for real time and accelerated stability studies as per ICH guidelines. These tablets were found to be stable even after 6 months of stability study as all the parameters were within limit as per the specifications.

KEYWORDS: Diabetes, Grewia asiatica, Phalsa, Sharbat berry, Nutraceutical, Antidiabetic.

1. INTRODUCTION

Grewia asiatica L., commonly known as Phalsa has been scientifically reported to possess antidiabetic properties, supported by several preclinical and biochemical studies. There are a few studies on Grewia which demonstrates its low Glycemic Index (GI) value of 5.34. Due to its hypoglycemic effect, it helps in reducing blood sugar levels and is highly nutritive in managing diabetes. The fruit also has polyphenols which helps in reducing the high blood sugar levels in diabetes patients.

Grewia asiatica L. is a tropical fruit-bearing species widely distributed across South and Southeast Asia, including India, Nepal, Thailand, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Myanmar, Cambodia, China, Laos, and Vietnam. It is extensively cultivated for its edible berries and its diverse nutraceutical and medicinal applications. The fruit pulp contains approximately 80.8 g of water, 1.3 g of protein, 0.9 g of fat, 14.7 g of carbohydrates, 1.2 g of

fiber, and essential minerals such as calcium, phosphorus, and iron per 100 g. The fruit and seeds are nutritionally rich, containing 18 amino acids, with aspartic acid, glutamic acid, and leucine being the most predominant. Additionally, the fruit is a notable source of vitamins A and C and is enriched with various bioactive phytochemicals, including anthocyanins, tannins, phenolics, and flavonoids.

Pharmacologically, *Grewia asiatica* exhibits a wide spectrum of biological activities, such as antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, anticancer, antioxidant, antidiabetic, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, antiemetic, radioprotective, hepatoprotective, antihyperlipidemic, immunomodulatory, sedative, hypnotic, and nootropic effects. Owing to this broad range of therapeutic properties, *Grewia asiatica* has garnered increasing scientific and commercial attention in recent years. Its extracts are now being utilized by several pharmaceutical

and nutraceutical industries for the development of safe, cost-effective, and readily available health-promoting formulations.

The fruit extract of *Grewia asiatica* L. was formulated into immediate-release tablets. Mannitol was incorporated as a diluent, while three superdisintegrants—Croscarmellose Sodium, Crospovidone, and Sodium Starch Glycolate—were included to enhance tablet disintegration. The fruit extract itself exhibited inherent binding properties; therefore, no additional binder was required. Colloidal Silicon Dioxide served as a glidant, and Magnesium Stearate was added as a lubricant. Purified water was used as the granulation solvent.

Crospovidone, and Sodium Starch Glycolate—were included to enhance tablet disintegration. The fruit extract itself exhibited inherent binding properties; therefore, no additional binder was required. Colloidal Silicon Dioxide served as a glidant, and Magnesium Stearate was added as a lubricant. Purified water was used as the granulation solvent.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Table 1: Raw Materials, Quantities and their function.

S. No.	Raw Materials	Quantity (mg/tablet)	Function
1.	<i>Grewia asiatica</i> Fruit Extract	500.00	Active Ingredient / Binder
2.	Mannitol	300.00	Diluent
3.	Croscarmellose Sodium	20.00	Superdisintegrant
4.	Crospovidone	20.00	Superdisintegrant
5.	Sodium Starch Glycolate	20.00	Superdisintegrant
6.	Colloidal Silicon Dioxide	25.00	Glidant
7.	Magnesium Stearate	15.00	Lubricant
8.	Purified Water	Q.S.	Solvent
	Total	1000.00 mg	

3. Manufacturing Process

3.1. Sieving, Mixing, Granulation, and Lubrication

Grewia asiatica extract, Mannitol, and 50% of each superdisintegrants were passed through a #40 mesh and blended in a Rapid Mixer Granulator (RMG) for 5 minutes at slow speed. Purified water was used as the granulating solvent. Wet granulation was performed in the RMG until the desired end-point was achieved.

The wet mass was screened through a #16 mesh and dried in a Fluidized Bed Dryer (FBD) at an inlet temperature of 55°C until the moisture content decreased to below 3%. The dried granules were rescreened

through a #20 mesh and blended with the remaining superdisintegrants in the RMG for 5 minutes.

Colloidal Silicon Dioxide and Magnesium Stearate were passed through a #60 mesh and added for lubrication. Lubrication was carried out in the RMG for **45 seconds**.

Moisture Content and Flow Properties

The moisture content of the lubricated granules was determined using a Denver Digital Moisture Analyzer at 105°C. Flow property was evaluated by the angle of repose.

Table 2: Moisture Content and Angle of Repose.

S. No.	Parameter	Result
1	Moisture Content (Lubricated Granules)	3.02%
2	Angle of Repose (θ)	26° 18'

Pre-compression Parameters

Pre-compression characteristics were evaluated using an Electrolab USP Tapped Density Tester.

Table 3: Pre-compression Parameters of Lubricated Granules.

S. No.	Parameter	Result
1	Bulk Density	0.45 g/cc
2	Tapped Density	0.55 g/cc
3	Carr's Index	14.13%
4	Hausner's Ratio	1.16

Carr's Index < 15% and Hausner's Ratio < 1.25 indicate **good flowability**.

4. Compression of Tablets

The lubricated granules were compressed using a Karnavati 9-station double-rotary tablet punching machine equipped with oblong, biconvex punch tooling (20.5 × 10.0 mm, plain). Machine speed was maintained at 15 RPM, and the average tablet weight was 1000 mg. All in-process parameters including hardness, thickness,

friability, and weight variation remained within acceptable limits.

5. Evaluation of Compressed Tablets

5.1. Hardness

Tablet hardness was measured using a Campbell Electronics digital hardness tester. Hardness was

maintained between **90–110 N**, ensuring mechanical stability during handling, packaging, and transportation.

5.2. Thickness

Tablet thickness was controlled to prevent packing and blistering issues. Measurements taken using a Dial Vernier Caliper showed a range of **6.2–6.6 mm**, with an average of **6.5 mm**.

5.3. Weight Variation

The weight variation of the batches complied with pharmacopoeial limits ($\pm 7.5\%$).

5.4. Friability

Friability was evaluated using an Electrolab Tablet Friability Tester. The tablets showed a friability value of **0.3%**, indicating excellent mechanical strength (<1% is acceptable).

5.5. Disintegration Time

Disintegration testing was performed using a Veego Disintegration Test Apparatus in water maintained at **37 \pm 2°C**. One tablet was placed in each of the six tubes of the basket.

- Minimum disintegration time: **7 min 30 sec**
- Maximum disintegration time: **9 min 40 sec**
- Average disintegration time: **8 min 35 sec**

The tablets demonstrated acceptable disintegration for an immediate-release formulation.

CONCLUSION

The *Grewia asiatica* fruit extract was successfully formulated into stable, immediate-release tablets using wet granulation. The extract itself exhibited adequate binding capacity, eliminating the need for additional binders, while mannitol and selected superdisintegrants ensured good compressibility and rapid disintegration. The pre-compression parameters, including moisture content, angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's Index, and Hausner's Ratio, demonstrated that the granules possessed excellent flow and compression characteristics.

All post-compression evaluation parameters—hardness, friability, thickness, weight uniformity, and disintegration time—remained within acceptable pharmacopoeial limits. The tablets showed strong mechanical integrity with low friability, consistent weight and thickness, and an average disintegration time suitable for immediate-release dosage forms.

Overall, the formulation approach yielded high-quality *Grewia asiatica* extract tablets with desirable physical properties, confirming that the chosen excipient blend and processing conditions were appropriate for producing robust and effective herbal tablets.

REFERENCES

1. Elnazeer I. Hamedelniei *et al.* Formulation and Evaluation of Grewia Tenax Fruits as Effervescent tablets for treatment of Iron Deficiency Anemia, International Journal of Development Research, 2020; 10(2): 34084-34090.
2. Indian Pharmacopoeia (I.P.), 2024; 1, 2 & 3.
3. United States Pharmacopoeia (U.S.P.), 2025; 1 and 2.
4. Handbook of Pharmaceutical Excipients 6th edition, 2009.
5. Ding X, Robinson JR. Extended release and targeted drug delivery system. In Remington: The Science and Practice of Pharmacy. 20th edition, Gennaro; A. R., Ed. Lippincott Williams and Wilkins, 2000; 1: 939.
6. Gilbert S Banker and Christopher T Rhodes. Modern Pharmaceutics, 4th edition, 504 (2002).
7. Abhishek Raj. Formulation and in-vitro evaluation of Voglibose dispersible tablets. European journal of biomedical and pharmaceutical sciences, 2016; 3(2); 226 - 230.
8. Abhishek Raj. Formulation and in-vitro evaluation of fast disintegrating Levocetirizine Dihydrochloride tablets, Journal of Atoms and Molecules, 2015; 5(2): 910 - 915.
9. Abhishek Raj and Dr. Amit Sharma Design and Development of Bilayer Tablets of Metformin Hydrochloride Sustained Release and Glimperide Immediate Release for the treatment of type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, International Journal of Clinical Studies and Medical Case Reports, 2022; 21(2): 1-7.
10. Abhishek Raj and Dr. Amit Sharma (2025) Nutraceutical and Health-Promoting Effects of Grewia asiatica L., An Edible Fruit Plant, World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(9): 286-294.
11. Raj A and Sharma A, A Review on Diabetes Mellitus, Sun Text Review of Biotechnology, 2024; 5(1): 150.
12. Swain, S., et al. (2023). Recent progress on phytochemistry and pharmacological properties of Grewia asiatica. [Pharmacology/Phytochemistry review].
13. Classification and Diagnosis of Diabetes Mellitus: Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes. Diabetes Care, 2018; 41(Suppl 1): S13-S27.
14. Khattab, H. A. H., et al. (2015). Antihyperglycemic potential of Grewia asiatica fruit extract against streptozotocin-induced hyperglycemia in rats: anti-inflammatory and antioxidant mechanisms. Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity, 2015, Article 549743.
15. American Diabetes Association Report of the expert committee on the diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus. Diabetes Care, 1998; 21: S5-S19.
16. Mehmood, A., et al. Nutraceutical perspectives and value addition of phalsa (*Grewia asiatica*): a review. Journal of Food Biochemistry, 2020; 44: e13228.

17. Pharmaceutical dosage forms: Tablets, Revised and Expanded: Lieberman, Lachman and Schwartz, Vol – I, 2nd edition.
18. The theory and practice of Industrial Pharmacy. 3rd edition: Lachman, Luberman and Kanig, Lea Febiger P – 66 – 68.
19. Remington, The science and practice of pharmacy: Twentieth Edition, 903-914.
20. Podczeck F, Drake KR, Neton JM, Harian I. The strength of bi-layered tablet. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2008; 1-14.
21. Mohammed Elhassan and Yagi, S.M. (2010). Nutritional Composition of *Grewia* Species (*Grewiatenax* (Forsk) Fiori, *G. flavescens* Juss and *G. villosa* Willd) Fruits, *Advance Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 2010; 2(3): 159-162.
22. Aboagarib, E.A.A., Yang, R., Hua, X., Siddeeg, A. Chemical compositions, nutritional properties and volatile compounds of Guddaim (*Grewiatenax* Forssk) Fiori fruits. *J. Food Nutr. Res.*, 2014; 2(4): 187-192.
23. Suliman, Z.E.A., Zidan, N.S. and Foudah, S.H.I., 2018. Chemical Compositions, Antioxidant, and Nutritional Properties of the Food Products of Guddaim (*Grewiatenax*). *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research & Allied Sciences*, 2018; 7(3): 172-182.
24. Gebauer, J. K. El-Siddig, E.I., Tahir, B. A., Salih, A., Ebert, G. and Hammer, K. Exploiting the Potential of Indigenous Fruit Trees: *Grewiatenax* (Forssk.) Fiori in Sudan, *Genet Resource Crop E.*, 2007; 54: 1701–1708.